

An innovative approach to computer mathematics teaching in a large engineering class

Isabel Espírito Santo, Cristiano Jesus

ALGORITMI Centre, Department of Production and Systems, School of Engineering, University of Minho, Guimarães, Portugal

Email: iapinho@dps.uminho.pt, b12121@algoritmi.uminho.pt

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Abstract

This work describes the changes in a CU (curricular unit), Numerical Methods, that occurs in the second semester of the second year in the master's programme of mechanical engineering, in 2020-2021. The methodology used in this CU was obsolete and has been taught with expositive classes and practical classes with little participation of the students. The big challenges are the dimension of the class (112 students), the lack of motivation to the subject of the CU and the fact that the CU appears very early in the teaching programme. This turned out to be even harder with the migration to online teaching, due to the pandemic and the uncertainty of the remaining of the semester (at this point we still don't know if a blended learning system is going to be possible). The CU is working with some technological resources such as padlet, PollEv, BlackBoard and Ted Ed. The strategies being implemented are Problem-Based Learning (PBL), Audience Response Systems (ARS) and it has been used a partial flipped classroom strategy. Every week there are small videos available, to introduce the subjects and engage the students, and other videos are recorded in the Blackboard platform during the more expositive and complex parts of the classes, as well as exercises (by hand or in MATLAB™). In terms of assessment, there are weekly mini-tests, some of them in MATLAB™, preceded by a preparation quiz in the platform PollEv in a session before the class to maintain the students' engagement. There is a small project in MATLAB™ where the students in teams are encouraged to search for an applied problem from the real world in the suggested routine. There are two planned face-to-face tests, one of them already took place. In the practical classes, the students are divided in smaller classes, where they can practice with the teacher (these classes had now migrated to a face-to-face scenario). The results until this point are very promising, with a wide participation of the students and excellent scores in the mini-tests.

Keywords: Active Learning; Engineering Education; Problem-Based Learning (PBL); Audience Response System (ARS)

1 Introduction

According to the assumptions raised in the literature, this article aims to present a report of experiences about the realization of the perspective of learning mathematics as a "process of individual construction and as a process of acculturation in relation to the mathematical meanings and practices" in a given social environment. These experiences were carried out in the context of Engineering Education, in a curricular unit (CU) of the mathematics area, namely Numerical Methods, which took place in the second semester of the second year in the master's program of Mechanical Engineering, in the second semester of the academic year 2020-2021.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. In section 2 is presented the theoretical background for systematization of the concepts that support the educational methodologies adopted. In section 3 is made a contextualization to the actual problem. Section 4 presents the learning methodologies, strategies and assessment methods adopted and in section 5 some preliminary results are presented. The paper is finished with some recommendations and final remarks in Section 6.

2 Theoretical Background

Khait (2005) states that in recent years, the mathematics-related competences needed for the demands of work have become increasingly associated with computerization and information saturation in the social environment. The "de-mathematization" of society has occurred through the transfer of traditional roles from mathematical professionals to calculators and computers. However, the demands for cognitive skills related to mathematics have grown because of the need to behave appropriately in today's technologically sophisticated environment. For Khait (2005), the need for the development of mathematical language competences has

become more urgent in the context of the computer revolution. The ubiquity of computer applications and human-machine interaction increase the importance of mathematics education for modern society. In this context, the competent worker in high-tech industries is the one who is able to construct new definitions and understand the definitions constructed by their colleagues, and the job of an information technology professional is to make the transition between formal (human-machine) and informal (human-human) communication.

In this context, researchers and agents responsible for mathematics education have made important reflections about their performance and about students' behaviour. Boaler (1999) draws attention to the fact that students not only develop a behaviour, but a behaviour that is appropriate to a particular community that constitutes the classroom. He considers the following behaviours to be the most common in classrooms: (i) when students must solve exercises, they expect that using the methods they have learned on the blackboard is the appropriate procedure; (ii) if a question requires knowledge of the real world, or knowledge unrelated to mathematics, students consider that they should stop and ask for help; (iii) students always expect to use all the content they have studied on the blackboard, or all the symbols in a diagram, and so on. According to this author, when students encounter situations in textbooks that do not fit their expectations in terms of behaviour, they become confused, not because they do not understand the mathematical issues involved in the questions, but because they are not used to deal with situations that do not follow a dynamic of reproduction and classification. They rarely select the information they need, but always expect that they must apply exactly the procedures they have learned on the blackboard. He further reports that the alignment that students make between requirements and possibilities in mathematics classes also has major implications for their real-world use of mathematics. Students often report that in their day-to-day jobs they face completely different challenges than they do in the classroom.

Khait (2005) considers that there are different educational perspectives on mathematics, among which the most common are, (1) the one that is based on the view that mathematics deals with subjects that can be objects of an exact theory, thus corresponding to a set of rules that must be applied to solve problems, and (2) the approach that treats mathematics as a language and a way of thinking, thus that it is a method whose boundaries adapt according to circumstances. The latter interpretation implies that what makes a word or an expression belong to mathematics is not its exact meaning, but the way in which this meaning is perceived. In this respect, mathematics should be understood as correctable, fallible, and socially changeable.

According to Cobb *et al.* (1992), learning mathematics can be seen as a process of individual construction and acculturation in relation to the mathematical meanings and practices of a certain society. Since the teacher is the only member of the constituted classroom community who evaluates the students' construction process as a potential basis for learning, it is therefore incumbent upon the teacher to facilitate discussions around mathematics among students while acting as a participant who legitimates certain aspects of mathematical activity and sanctions others. In this way, the teacher acts directly on each student's constraints on the interpretations and solutions of mathematical challenges, in a context of communication that involves the explicit negotiation of mathematical meanings.

Thus, we can summarize from Boaler (1999), that theories of Mathematics Education initially focused attention on individuals and on mathematics in order to advocate the repetition of mathematical behaviours and later on the construction of knowledge with the individual as the central element. For the author, these perspectives suggest that students' behaviours and practices in situations involving mathematics are not just mathematical, nor are they individual, but are emergent from a relationship formed by people and systems.

For Khait (2005), in opposition to the Platonic and formalistic point of view, mathematics should be understood as a human activity, a social phenomenon, part of culture, historically involved and intelligible only in the social context. The author points out that what maintains the unity of a scientific community does not need to be a set of beliefs. In fact, the sharing of beliefs is far less common than the sharing of practices, precisely because the sharing of practices depends on the sharing of beliefs, not the other way around.

Malloy & Malloy (1998) say that culture is the sharing of meanings, but not necessarily of consensus. Therefore, culture is values and beliefs that are embedded in the way people in a community think and act, and in the

tools they use. In the past, educational environments were thought of in a way that made differences difficult. The term used to describe the ability to adjust to new cultures is "adaptation," and the authors believe that students must develop this ability and practice it in the various cultures that identify classrooms and disciplines, so if the environment does not yet provide for the coexistence of differences, it must change.

Schubring (2011) mentions the "humanization of mathematics," a very present thought in research on mathematics education in recent history, a goal pursued by many who are dedicated to finding ways to turn this idea into a concrete reality.

For Boaler (1999), the effectiveness of a classroom community involves the adherence of the educational environment and the rules of mathematics to the interpretation of non-mathematical issues and the suppression of certain attitudes. Students should be encouraged to develop independence over their actions and over their paces of action. Instead of the quantity of mathematical experiences and the requirement for repetition, the quality of these experiences should be observed and students should be helped to engage in finding skills to deal with them collaboratively in interpersonal activities. Thus, the author considers that a number of strategies unrelated to learning contribute to success in the classroom since in this environment students not only learn mathematical concepts and procedures, but also learn to interact, and to develop a set of beliefs and ways of proceeding, appropriate to behaviour in the face of mathematical challenges.

For Malloy & Malloy (1998), traditionally, mathematics, as an academic subject, may be at the level of algorithms to be reproduced and procedures to be followed. Even there, the prospect of a culture of mathematical thinking may be present, however, only those who demonstrate a superior understanding of that culture are chosen to receive some sort of mentoring, development, enrichment activities, opportunities for exploration, and access to more advanced mathematical problems. Others who demonstrate limitations are relegated to performing a script of mathematical practices that do not necessarily signify learning, much less inclusion in the mathematical culture.

Malloy & Malloy (1998) consider that the social, cultural, and historical context in which students live define and format their experiences. The personal and knowledge culture may conflict with the scientific way of validating knowledge, and when related to mathematics learning, it impacts the students' self-perception as members of a mathematics community. Therefore, for the authors, what defines the inclusion or exclusion of members to this community are three factors: screening, impersonal conditions, and language. In this context, students' success in class depends on their ability to understand and participate in the culture of those in power, since in a way the academic environment reproduces the culture of society at large in structure, rules, and hegemony. Therefore, Malloy & Malloy (1998) argue that the classroom atmosphere should provide opportunities for students to experience mathematics socially by confronting appropriate levels of challenge, meaningful goals, opportunities for risk-taking, and a variety of strategies so that they overcome obstacles through the use of mathematics communication in a classroom designed with a strategy that values variation in organization and a pedagogy that offers students the possibility of adjusting to diverse learning styles, such as holistic perspective, free thinking, and others. Students should be encouraged to seek a big picture view, to improvise and use intuitive thinking, to verbalize their ideas, and to engage them in social interaction with discussions, independent goal construction, and their own pathways for knowledge expression.

Tawfik & Lilly (2015) stress that the main goal of education is to prepare students to construct solutions in a given domain of practice to overcome authentic problems. Therefore, it is important that students have contact with challenges, constraints and perspectives that practitioners experience. The authors believe that this pedagogical approach allows students to take ownership of knowledge and its construction process in a way that enables them to adopt an active role in the educational experience. One way to facilitate this educational strategy is through the engendering of self-learning skills supported by learning technologies.

Tawfik & Lilly (2015) present the so-called "flipped classroom" methodology that has these attributes. According to DeLozier & Rhodes (2017), flipped classroom is a teaching method in which the classroom organization logic is inverted so that the consumption of content takes place in advance, through online learning, and the classroom meetings are dedicated to interaction, clarification of doubts, group activities, and others. Thus, flipped classroom is so named precisely because it subverts the traditional model of teaching and

learning. In the latter, the content is consumed in the classroom and the activities must be performed at home. In the proposed model this dynamic is inverted. The content must be studied at home and the classroom must be the space for interaction and exercises. In this case, the teacher is a mediator of effective learning practices. The most recommended practice for teachers is to record lectures in short videos or other multimedia resources that can be made available to students online.

According Tawfik & Lilly (2015), the flipped classroom model applied in conjunction with other resources such as Problem Based Learning (PBL) can provide a just-in-time basis for learning in a way that engages students effectively in finding solutions to real or similar problems that are common in real life. For these authors a key element of PBL is structured problems that have multiple constraints, can be observed from different perspectives, and provide multiple potential solutions. This approach focuses on authentic contexts and postulates that learning should be experience-based and situated within a domain. Thus, students take an active role in the learning process, use technologies that enable autonomy, develop knowledge construction through elementary guided inquiry, experience real-world problem solving, and interact collaboratively to reach creative solutions.

For DeLozier & Rhodes (2017) the flipped classroom is a student-centred education method, that is, the students are responsible for studying the content by themselves and the face-to-face meetings should be opportunities for discussion, which also does not take away the student's protagonism. This discussion can be carried out in various ways, such as audience response, open questions, individual or paired quizzes, pair and share activities, student presentations. The authors state that prior study of the content can be accomplished through videotaped lectures by the teachers.

3 Context

This experiment took place with a class of 112 students of Mechanical Engineering. The Curricular Unit (CU) is Numerical Methods and occurs in the second curricular year of this master's programme. This CU consists in advanced mathematics and appears too soon in the course, which is an added difficulty, due to the maturity of the students at this stage of the course. The ideal would be that this CU appeared at least in the third year of the course.

The classes occurred in a traditional and obsolete context until now. The quick emerging of the online classes due to the pandemic appeared as an opportunity to modernize the CU and implement some new methodologies to motivate the students for a CU that typically they don't like, because it is difficult and it is not specific to their course. At the middle of last year's second semester a quick migration to online classes obliged to implement some different strategies, that are being pursued this year. All of these methodologies are easily transferred for the presential context, that will occur predictably in the last third of the semester.

4 Learning methodologies, strategies and assessment methods

4.1 Availability of materials

The important informations and materials about the classes are in a padlet. This includes the presentation of the professors in the team, curricular program of the CU, recommended bibliography, overall planification, problems to solve (by hand or in MATLAB™), mini-projects to each group, assessment details and links to the tools used in the classes, such as instructions to use MATLAB™ online, TED-Ed, PollEverywhere, and Blackboard. This padlet can be found in <https://padlet.com/isabelpinhoespiritasantojgg4q5kvq3tiuf4y>.

There is a second padlet, where the students can find the planning and more detailed instructions to each week, working as a road map to the classes and study. It contains, among other things, the slides used in the expositive part of the cases, the solutions to the proposed problems each week and the videos (of the expositive part of the classes, resolution of exercises and problems solved with MATLAB™). As a complement, each week is offered a music that is contextualized with each class and environment lived at the moment with

the pandemic, to help to give a more embracing, broader and more human point of view to the subjects usually approached in the CU. This padlet can be accessed in <https://padlet.com/isabelpinhoespiritoso/Bookmarks>.

4.2 Flipped Classroom

It was introduced a kind of hybrid flipped classroom to engage the students in the resolution of the problems. The subject is complex and they need some help to understand the basic theoretical concepts. Some introductory and simple videos were provided the week previous to the class, as well as the pages from the support text that they should study. The first synchronous weekly moment, that occurs on Mondays with the entire class, is devoted to a brief exposure of the more important theoretical concepts, to consolidate the videos and text they were proposed to prepare ahead of the class. It is presented as well a practical example solved with the presented algorithm, and using the adequate MATLAB™ routine. This way the students may interfere and question the parts that they don't understand and sometimes they can share with each other their perceptions. These classes are always recorded, so the students can return to them latter if they need to. The second class (face-to-face since 19th of April), was devoted to solve practical exercises, introducing a PBL methodology. A problem is proposed, in the subject at hand, and the students have to solve it, alone or in groups, discussing the results among them. The teacher is essentially a moderator, pointing the right direction, giving suggestions and sometimes helping to correct some mistakes. This was more effective in the face-to-face context, but in the online classes it was asked to the students to speak and sometimes ARS were used to facilitate the communication.

4.3 Audience Response Systems

The most difficult thing in the online classes is to have feedback from the students. Usually, I have 100 black squares in total silence. The way I found to turn this issue around was implementing ARSs. A simple question like "did you all understand?" was inevitably followed by total silence. I do the same question but in a quick quiz in the Blackboard with two possible answers: yes/no. It is amazing the change that this simple practice brought to the classes. I can assess if it is necessary to dig deeper into the issue at hand until there are only yesses. The students are divided in three different practical classes, that occur on Thursdays, where they can dialogue with the teacher to explore and solve exercises. To incentivise the participation of the students, an Audience Response System (ARS) is also implemented (the PollEv platform). This way, the students are invited to share their results in an anonymous way. According to the answers some are invited to share their conclusions with the colleagues. There are also facultative sessions where the students may again practice and ask questions to the teacher and to each other. The teacher mediates these sessions also with PollEv.

4.4 Assessment

This is probably the bigger change in the CU. Traditionally the students used to have only a written test (15/20) and a MATLAB™ test (5/20). The online assessment brought difficulties, that were also a huge opportunity to improve the assessment methodology, maintaining the equity and fairness to all of the students.

The main idea was to divide part of the assessment (6/20) into 8 small mini-tests of 5/6 questions of multiple choice (4 possible answers) during 10 minutes, before each class. This works as formative tests more than a summative evaluation. It is assumed that the students talk between them, since they are at home, but the effect in terms of scores is negligible and they learn either way, which is the most important issue at this point. Also, each of the 5 questions in a mini-test has 20 versions of equivalent degree of difficulty, and the test is generated randomly, giving rise to 20^5 (3,200,000) different possible tests. Also, the order of the questions is random, as well as the order of the possible answers. The probability of a student to have success in a test (considering success achieving 3 or more questions correct) is only 1.56%, and when considering all of the 8 mini-tests it drops to only 0.06%, using a binomial distribution.

The MATLAB™ assessment is made with 4 mini-tests (4/20) and also with a group project of 4 students (4/20). They are divided into 4 themes and are invited to find a real-world problem that fits that specific theme, solve the problem using the software and write a small report about the problem itself, the technique used to solve it and the conclusions they take from it. The themes explored were non-linear equations and systems, function approximation, numerical integration and differential equations. The students present essentially problems

from the mechanical engineering context. This way they can see the applicability of what they are learning in a more real context, giving rise to much more motivation, that was observed in the students that had already finished their projects. All of the above implied 63 banks of tests with 20 questions each (1260 questions in total), that were prepared and implemented in Blackboard, only for the online assessments.

Finally, they had 2 face-to-face assessment moments (6/20).

5 Results

Since the CU is still, these results are only preliminary. It was implemented an intermediate quiz to evaluate the student's satisfaction with the implemented changes.

5.1 Attendance to the classes

It was noticed a much higher presence of the students in the synchronous classes, as it can be confirmed in Figure 1 by the students' responses and as it was observed by the teachers. This is a great challenge because in this stage of the semester all the classes are online, and the main parts were recorded and made available latter, which could lead to a lower attendance. This was not observed at all. The students understood perfectly the advantage of the synchronous moments to clarify aspects that can be more challenging, and to solve problems in the presence of the teachers, to ask for help if needed. Also, they have the possibility to assist to the classes latter (Figure 2), since they were recorded. To have a comparison basis, Table 1 shows the difference in classes attendance, also compared with the previous 2 academic years, in percentage.

Figure 1. Attendance to the online classes.

Figure 2. Use of the online classes recording.

Table 1. Comparison of the attendance to the classes in the last 3 academic years.

	2020/2021	2019/2020	2018/2019
Always/almost always	70,7	47,7	55,6
Sometimes	20,7	25,5	35,6
Few times	6,2	4,8	6,7
Never	2,4	2,4	2,2

Figure 3 shows how much the students use the padlet. There is also a very positive response with 50% using it a lot and 41,5% using it sometimes. None of the students claims that never uses the padlet.

Figure 3. Use of the padlet.

5.2 Classifications

Until now, the students did 5 mini-testes (3.5/20), 2 MATLAB™ tests (2/20) and a face-to-face test (3/20). Also, 16 students already submitted their mini-project (4/20). From de 112 students, 99 chose to do the continuous assessment, 83 of them where already evaluated to 8.5/20 and 16 of them to 12.5/20. Figure 4 shows the results until now (in percentage) compared to the two previous academic years. It should be stressed that the previous years include also the assessment by exam (the students have two more chances of being evaluated after the CU is finished). In 2019/20 (with 120 evaluated students) more than half of the semester was online, with all the assessment online, so some of the strategies herein presented had to be used. In 2018/2019 (with 109 evaluated students) it was used a purely classical approach as previously described.

Figure 4. Grades in Numerical Methods for the last 3 academic years

5.3 Students Assessment to the CU

Figures 5 and 6 are about the number of mini-tests and MATLAB™ tests, respectively. The majority of the students is happy with the number of assessment elements. However, some of them (18,3%) thinks there should be less mini-tests and 6.1% thinks that should be less MATLAB™ tests. Only 6,1% have the opinion that there should not be mini-tests at all. None of them thinks that should there not be MATLAB™ tests, and even 3.7% thinks that they should have more of these tests.

Figure 5: The mini-tests should be...

Figure 6: The MATLAB tests should be ...

The quiz also had two fields where the students could write freely positive and negative aspects about the organization of the CU. 58 students pointed positive aspects, being the most frequent the assessment method (26), the organization of the CU (22), the quality of the classes (21) and the relation teacher-student (20). Less than 10 students referred the recording of the classes, the PolleEv and the use of MATLAB™. 25 students pointed negative aspects being the excessive number of mini-tests the most frequent with 12 students referring it, which reinforces what is shown in Figure 5. It is clear that a large majority is happy with the assessment and organization of the CU, and the attendance to the classes also improved tremendously.

6 Final Remarks

The goal of transforming mathematics into a process of individual construction and a process of acculturation in relation to mathematical meanings and practices in the context of professional action in Mechanical Engineering has become a double challenge. First, because this approach requires a change of mentality both

from teachers, and from the students whose behaviour, for the most part, reflects the conditioning of passive learning based on the memorization of content and the trained application of mathematical techniques for subsequent reproduction of these operations in tests and examinations. Second, because the pandemic period through which all are passing, and which demands the absolutely new practice of teleclassing, inevitably provokes doubt about the viability of these objectives under these conditions.

However, what at first glance seemed a rather significant difficulty turned into a great opportunity to implement practices, such as Flipped Classroom and Audience Response Systems, with the help of educational technological tools. The atypical conditions for carrying out the teaching and learning process cancelled the impulse of resistance to change that would probably happen under normal conditions.

Although the experiment was a success, there needs to be continuity and exploration of new ways to realize the goal of building autonomy through exploration with mutual collaboration among students to discover mathematical solutions when faced with real-world challenges.

In a non-pandemic environment, ideally, the students can use the classes to discuss the problems more freely in groups, since they don't have to maintain the social distance. The flipped classroom seemed a very useful tool to engage the students in a more autonomous work, using the time with the teacher to consolidate the acquired knowledge. Also, the mini-tests seemed a precious tool to maintain the students interested in the CU during all the semester and not only in the previous days to the final test.

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